

Preparation and standardization of Ceric ammonium sulfate standard solution

Manisha Chaudhari, HOD, Kokan Gyanpeeth Rahul Dharkar College of Pharmacy and Research Institute, Karjat

Citation: [10.5281/zenodo.10851169](https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10851169)

Also available at: pharmacyinfo.com/ceric-ammonium-sulfate-standard-solution/

Preparation and standardization of Ceric ammonium sulfate standard solution

Aim

To Prepare and standardize 0.1 M Ceric ammonium sulfate standard solution

Principle

This is an example of Cerimetric titration. Ceric ammonium sulphate or Ceric ammonium nitrate in sulphuric acid medium can function as strong oxidizing agent and considerably more stable than standard potassium permanganate solution and have a high oxidation potential. Sufficient sulphuric acid is to be used to prevent hydrolysis and precipitation of basic salts. In place of sulphuric acid, hydrochloric acid may also be used. It cannot interfere with analytical application.

Ceric ammonim sulphate, a salt of suitable solubility for the preparation of the standard solution has the approximate formula $Ce(SO_4)_2 \cdot 2(NH_4)_2SO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$, but the solution has to be standardized against a solution of Arsenic trioxide. Since ceric ammonium sulphate is a strong oxidizing agent, we can determine various reducing substances by simple titration. In presence of a reducing agent, it undergoes reduction to the cerous state.

Procedure

Preparation of 0.1 M Ceric ammonium sulphate standard solution

Dissolve ___ gm of ceric ammonium sulphate, with the aid of gentle heat, in a mixture of 30 ml of sulphuric acid and 500 ml of water. Cool, filter the solution, if turbid, and dilute to 1000 ml with water.

Standardization of 0.1 M Ceric ammonium sulphate standard solution

Weigh accurately about 0.2 g of arsenic trioxide, previously dried at 105 ° for 1 hour, and transferred to a 500-ml conical flask. Wash down the inner walls of the flask with 25 ml of 8.0 per cent w/v solution of sodium hydroxide, swirl to dissolve, add 100 ml of water and mix.

Add 30 ml of dilute sulphuric acid, 0.15 ml of osmic acid solution, 0.1 ml of ferroin sulphate solution and slowly titrate with the ceric ammonium sulphate solution

The end point is pink colour to a very pale blue. Add the titrant slowly towards the end-point.

Reference

Indian Pharmacopoeia 2007; Vol. 1; Pg. No.313